

Reaction kinetics on hydrolysis of substituted di-phenyl phosphate ester in different borate buffers

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Abstract : The reaction of hydroxide ion with di-4-methyl phenyl phosphate has been studied in the presence of micelles of cationic detergent. It has been investigated at pH 8.0 to 10.0 at 40 ± 0.10 °C in aqueous dioxane di-phosphate esters. Pseudo-first order rate constants k_{ψ} and k'_{ψ} have been measured spectrophotometrically by rate of appearance of inorganic phosphate during hydrolysis. k_{ψ} and k'_{ψ} were rate constants with and without CTAB, which varied in between 0.02×10^{-3} to 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ and the concentration of phosphate was restricted to 5.0×10^{-3} s⁻¹. Rate constants increase with concentrations of CTAB, giving at rate maximum. $k_{\psi} = 67.03 \times 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹ at 18×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ CTAB and $k'_{\psi} = 52.43 \times 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹ at 16×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ CTAB respectively at pH 8.0 and 9.0 for di-anions of 4-mpp. The values of ion exchange parameter calculated at pH 8.0 and 9.0 by using various ion exchange equations have been summarized. The activation energy is 25.08 kcal/mol and entropy is 52.07 [-ΔS(eu)], which has been found at pH 8.0 and used borate buffer 3.9×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ [OH⁻].

Keywords : Borate buffer, hydrolysis, diphenyl phosphate ester, kinetics.

Introduction

In the present work a detailed kinetic analysis of nucleophilic cleavage of di-4-mpp in presence of cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide in water at 40 ± 0.1 °C was investigated. Our study was aimed at establishing the nature of factor responsible for the high rate of these processes.

Results and discussion

Di-phosphate ester reaction was strongly catalysed at different concentrations of cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB)⁸ at which effect of cationic micelles of CTAB on the rate constants of hydroxide ion with 4-mpp di-ester has been found as below :

Fig. 1a

The pseudo-first order rate constants for 4-mpp di-ester have been compared at two pHs 8.0 and 9.0. It has been observed that as detergent concentration increases, the value of rate constant also increases and attains a maximum 67.03×10^{-5} s⁻¹ and 52.43×10^{-5} s⁻¹ at 1.8×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ and 1.6×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ CTAB detergent concentration at pH 8.0 and 9.0 respectively. To calculate rate constant in terms of absorbances the rate expression may be given as below :

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{[A_{\infty}]}{A_{\infty} - x_1} \quad (1)$$

The relation between the observed pseudo-first order rate constants k_{ψ} and the surfactant concentration (D_n) for a spontaneous dephosphorylation of bis-4-mpp may be shown in the following Scheme A.

Scheme A

where S_w and S_m are substrates in aqueous and micellar pseudo phase respectively, k'_w and k'_m are the related first order rate constants and K_s and K'_s are the binding constants for aqueous and micellar pseudo phase.

The concentration of micellised surfactant $[D_n]$ is the total of surfactant concentration less than that of monomeric surfactant concentration. This is assumed to be given by critical micelle concentration (CMC)⁹, which proves that the equilibrium is maintained between substrate in micelle and water respectively. It is shown by following equation :

$$k = \frac{k'_w + k'_m K_s ([C_D] - \text{CMC})}{1 + K_s ([D_n] - \text{CMC})} \quad (2)$$

where the value of K_m can be obtained by analysis of the variation of K_s with D_n or by choosing conditions¹⁰, such that substrate is essential fully micellised surfactant is given by the following reaction :

$$D_n = C_D - \text{CMC}$$

where C_D is total concentration of the surfactant.

$$[M] = \frac{C_D - \text{CMC}}{N}$$

$$k_w = \frac{k'_w - k'_m \left(\frac{K_s}{N} \right) (C_D - \text{CMC})}{1 + \left(\frac{K_s}{N} \right) (C_D - \text{CMC})} \quad (3)$$

where N is the aggregation number and K_s is binding constant¹¹.

The above treatment assumes that only one substrate molecule is incorporated into such micelles. ' D_n ' an assumption, which is reasonable when the micelles are in large excess over the substrate. It has been used successfully for a number of spontaneous reactions but can be applied in a simple way for many reactions, which involves an external ionic reagent. As the rate constant increases with detergent concentration, the approximations generally lead to the maxima in the plot¹².

Where as eq. (1) predicts a rate plateau. The rate maxima have been explained in terms of ionic deactivation by the micelles in favourable cases. The binding constant K_s can be obtained directly¹³ according to the relation :

$$K_s = \frac{N}{(k'_m - k'_w)} \times \text{Slope } 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

Fig. 1b

The estimated value of $1/k_w - k'_w$ and $1/(C_D - \text{CMC})$ allows the determination of the value of k'_m , the rate constant in micelle and the binding constant K'_s for the reaction of 4-mpp with $[\text{OH}^-]$. The value of aggregation number $N = 61$ is taken from literature.

Quantitative treatment of the micelle induced reaction of $3.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH with $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ 4-mpp at pH 8.0 and temperature $40 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

The micelle induced hydrolysis has been found that hydrolysis is strongly dependent on the nature of the detergent. The initial counter ion presented in hydrolysis and "local concentration" of the system is due to the total contents of relative ion in the micellar pseudo phase.

To analyse the interfacial effect of the hydroxide ion with 4-mpp treatment of ion exchange in micellar solutions that explicitly considers the consequence of ion-exchange. This approach permits to analyse the effect that given experimental conditions will have on the concern and the kinetic behavior on exchangeable ionic reactants in micellar pseudo phase, because such effects have

been found to be strongly dependant on the detergent head group. The total content of the distribution of the reactants in micellar and aqueous pseudo phase ion exchange model, which have been represented previously by Scheme A.

Where the second order rate constants in each pseudo phase have been determined by taking into consideration of first order rate constants for over all reactions given by eq. (2), where K_w and K_m are first order rate constants in aqueous and micellar pseudo phase respectively.

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w + k_m K_s (D_n)}{1 + K_s (D_n)} \quad (4)$$

where K_s is binding constant, D_n is concentration of micellized surfactant respectively.

It is assumed that interaction of two or more counter ion anionic micelles is governed by ion exchange equilibrium as :

where 'm' and 'w' are in parent, which denote micellar and aqueous pseudo phase respectively.

Equilibrium or ion exchange constant for $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ denoted by $K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w (\text{OH}^-)_w + k_m K_s m_{\text{OH}}^{\text{S}} (D_n)}{1 + K_s (D_n)} \quad (6)$$

where m_{OH}^{S} is the concentration of the reaction ion in the micelle.

The fraction of head group $K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$ and β are assumed to be neutralized by counter ion and may be treated as independent of nature or concentration of counter ions.

For a mixture of $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$, β is identical with m_{OH}^{S} + m_{Br}^{S} , the concentration of $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]_w$ are expressed in term of total concentration in solution volume¹⁴, so that $[\text{OH}^-]_T$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_T$, can be substituting the value of $[\text{OH}^-]_m$, $[\text{OH}^-]_w$, $[\text{Br}^-]_w$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_m$ in eq. (5) leads to eq. (7).

$$[m_{\text{OH}}^{\text{S}}]^2 + m_{\text{OH}}^{\text{S}} \left[\frac{[\text{OH}^-]_T + K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}} [\text{Br}^-]_w}{[K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}} - 1][D_n]} - \beta \right] + \frac{\beta [\text{OH}^-]_T}{[K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}} - 1][D_n]} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Selecting the values of $K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$ and β as 10.0 and 0.75

respectively, m_{OH}^{S} has been calculated from the reaction at $3.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} [\text{OH}^-]$, by the eq. (8).

$$\frac{k_{\psi} - k'_w}{m_{\text{OH}}^{\text{S}} [D_n]} = k'_m K_s - K_s \frac{k_{\psi}}{m_{\text{OH}}^{\text{S}}} \quad (8)$$

These results suggest that pseudo phase ion exchange model can be applied as a first approximation to reactions of anions of 4-mpp with $[\text{OH}^-]$ in CTAB micelles.

Bi-molecular reaction of hydrophilic anionic nucleophilics $[\text{OH}^-]$ by hydroxylic solvents bond the hydrogen to anion concentration of anions at the surface of cationic micelles on the Stern¹⁵ layer have been calculated from the following equation :

$$[\text{OH}^-]_m = 1.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$[\text{Br}^-]_m = 1.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}} = 10$$

The concentration of anion of 4-mpp in micelles has been calculated from equation :

$$K_s = \frac{[4\text{-mpp}]_m}{[4\text{-mpp}]_w [D_n]}$$

This allows the determination of reaction substrate concentration of anions of 4-mpp in aqueous and pseudo phase as under.

$$[4\text{-mpp}]_m = 1.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$[4\text{-mpp}]_w = 1.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

Ion exchange parameter and second order rate constant for the reaction of 4-mpp with $[\text{OH}^-]$ in micellar pseudo phase at pH 8.0 and temperature $40 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ have been given as below :

$K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$	$[\text{OH}^-]_m 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{OH}^-]_T 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{OH}^-]_w 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)
10	1.32	3.9	3.78
m_{OH}^{S}	$K_s 10^3$	$K_m 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$K'_w 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)
0.14	1.06	5.76	9.48

The both aryl part of bis-4-methyl phenyl phosphate anion is deeply buried in inter ion of micelles and the phosphate anion are suitable exposed to nucleophilic attack by $[\text{OH}^-]$ ion, which is present in lower concentration in the micelle. Beside this, the anions of bis-4-mpp are hydrophobic and polarisable anions bind to micelles by the specific interaction but coulombic binding is much important in binding of hydrophilic anions. The anion of bis-4-mpp, which are not very hydrophilic but are

Comparative isokinetic rate data for the hydrolysis of some phosphate di-esters VIA their mono-negative species

Phosphate Di	Temp. (°C)	ΔE (kcal/mol)	Entropy [- ΔS (eu)]	Bond fission
4-Chloro-3,5-dimethylphenyl	40	19.52	13.76	P-O
4-Chloro-3-methylphenyl	40	18.14	18.81	P-O
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	98	22.89	28.80	P-O
2,4-Dichlorophenyl	98	17.50	45.30	P-O
3,5-Dimethylphenyl	98	23.79	33.60	P-O
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	98	18.70	25.00	P-O
Pentachlorophenyl	98	18.30	28.90	P-O
Isopropylphenyl	98	20.30	19.90	P-O
4-(2-Phenylisopropyl)phenyl	98	20.42	13.28	P-O
<i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>o</i> -cresylphenyl	98	19.71	29.70	P-O
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	40	25.08	52.07	P-O

polarisable, interact with oxygen linkage, present in zwitter ionic form of di-ester, forming hydrogen cyclic intermediate by entrap of [OH⁻] ion reducing the considerable coulombic interaction. This interaction by [OH⁻] ions in cationic micelles was ascribed to the higher surface charge density at cationic as compared with the anionic centres.

Experimental

We used phosphorus oxytrichloride and 4-methyl phenol for the preparation of di-4-methyl phenyl phosphate by the general method, in which phosphorus trichloride directly reacts with 4-methyl phenol. The product always contains a mixture of mono-, di- and tri-esters are extracted with ether solvent. Di-ester, was separated with 0.5 *N* NaOH solution. Analytical and IR spectral studies were made for the identification of di-ester, and kinetic studies have been done spectrophotometrically. We used ammonium molybdate solution and hydrogen borate reagent for kinetic studies. The amidol solution gradually decomposes, so fresh purified amidol solution was prepared when required. The solutions of pH 8.0, 9.0 and 10.0 were prepared in double distilled water. Di-ester was always prepared at 5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ solution of the compound. 5.0 ml di-ester solution was withdrawn for each run at definite intervals of time, in 25 ml standard flask which was immediately chilled in ice cold water to check further hydrolysis. For this 2.0 ml of amidol reagent and 1 ml of ammonium molybdate solution were introduced and total volume was made to 50 ml. 2.0 ml

buffer solutions were used at constant time intervals. After 7 min absorbances of fully developed blue colour was measured by spectrophotometer. Spectrum BX Series IR spectrophotometer was used for above experimental work.

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References

1. C. A. Banton, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Eng.*, 1979, 20, 11.
2. C. A. Banton, F. None, L. R. Romsted and F. H. Quina, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1991, 24, 1729.
3. T. C. Bruice, J. Katzhendler and L. R. Fedor, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 1333.
4. C. A. Banton and J. Ihera, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 42, 1865.
5. A. K. Yatsimirsky, K. Martinek and I. V. Berezin, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 2855.
6. Kallol K. Ghosh, Sancheeta Kolay, Manmohan L. Satnami, Sarah Moore, Raman Palepu and P. R. Dafonte, *J. Dis. Sci. and Tech.*, 2006, 28, 213.
7. C. A. Banton, N. D. Gillitt and H. J. Forondian, *Langmuir*, 1998, 14, 4415.
8. M. Patra and B. K. Sinha, *J. Macro. Sci., Part A : Pure and Appl. Chem.*, 2004, 37, 1601.
9. F. M. Monger and C. E. Protoy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 4698.

Note

10. E. V. Cordes and R. B. Duntop, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **2**, 329.
11. G. P. J. Panigrahi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 58.
12. T. C. Bruice, in "The Enzyme", 3rd ed., Academic Press, New York, 1970, **2**, 217.
13. C. A. Banton, L. Robinson, L. Sepulveda and M. J. Stem, *Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 1072.
14. S. S. Yadav and Adesh Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 991.
15. D. Stigter, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 3603.

